

Appendix B - Interview Guides

B.1 Interview Guide of Software Developers - Round 1

The developer and stakeholder interview guides were largely similar, with the primary distinction being the use of different terminology tailored to each group. For example, when interviewing developers, we focused on their interactions with stakeholders, and vice versa. The most notable difference, however, occurred between the interview rounds. In the second round, we prioritised questions on consequences early in the interviews to allocate more time to explore the consequences of empathy and lack of empathy.

1. Besides other developers, who are the stakeholders you are interacting with?
 - 1.1. Can you briefly explain what your interaction with them looks like?
 - 1.2. What is the mode of communication? How frequently do you meet?
2. What comes to your mind when you hear the word empathy? How do you describe empathy?
 - 2.1. What does empathy mean to you when interacting with these stakeholders?
3. When interacting with software developers, do you think these stakeholders need to practise empathy? Why?
4. Do you think empathy is relevant when considering your work and your interactions with these stakeholders? Why or why not? Please can you provide an example.
5. On a scale of 1 (useless) - 5 (useful), how would you rate empathy when interacting with stakeholders? Why?

Causes of empathy and lack of empathy:

6. Think of a time when these stakeholders empathised with you. In your experience, what made it easier for them to empathise with you? Please share an example.
7. Think of a time when you empathised with these stakeholders. In your experience, what made it easier for you to empathise with them? Please share an example.
8. Think of a time when these stakeholders did not empathise with you. In your experience, what made it difficult for them to empathise with you? Please share an example.
9. Think of a time when you did not empathise with these stakeholders. In your experience, what made it difficult for you to empathise with them? Please share an example.
10. Was there anything did to try and improve empathy? Why?
 - 10.1. Did you notice these empathy issues at the time?

Consequences of empathy and lack of empathy:

11. What did you experience when these stakeholders empathised with you?
 - 11.1. How did you feel?
 - 11.2. What happened as a result of their empathy?
 - 11.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?

- 11.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
- 12. What did you experience when you empathised with these stakeholders?
 - 12.1. What happened as a result of your empathy?
 - 12.2. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?
 - 12.3. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
- 13. What did you experience when these stakeholders were not empathetic towards you? What was that like?
 - 13.1. How did you feel?
 - 13.2. What happened due to their lack of empathy?
 - 13.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
 - 13.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
- 14. What did you experience when you did not show empathy towards stakeholders?
 - 14.1. What happened due to your lack of empathy?
 - 14.2. Have you had any negative experiences due to your lack of empathy?
 - 14.3. Have you had any positive experiences due to your lack of empathy?
- 15. What would you do to better empathise, or any strategies for mitigating the empathy barriers? What would work for you?
- 16. Is there anything else you would like to tell us?

B.2 Interview Guide of Software Stakeholders - Round 1

The developer and stakeholder interview guides were largely similar, with the primary distinction being the use of different terminology tailored to each group. For example, when interviewing developers, we focused on their interactions with stakeholders, and vice versa. The most notable difference, however, occurred between the interview rounds. In the second round, we prioritised questions on consequences early in the interviews to allocate more time to explore the consequences of empathy and lack of empathy.

- 1. Can you briefly explain what your interactions with developers look like?
 - 1.1. What is the mode of communication? How frequently do you meet?
- 2. What comes to your mind when you hear the word empathy? How do you describe empathy?
 - 2.1. What does empathy mean to you when interacting with developers?
- 3. When interacting with stakeholders, do you think software developers need to practise empathy? Why?
- 4. Do you think empathy is relevant when considering your work and your interactions with developers? Why or why not? Please can you provide an example.
- 5. On a scale of 1 (useless) - 5 (useful), how would you rate empathy when interacting with developers? Why?

Causes of empathy and lack of empathy:

6. Think of a time when developers empathised with you. In your experience, what made it easier for them to empathise with you? Please share an example.
7. Think of a time when you empathised with developers. In your experience, what made it easier for you to empathise with them? Please share an example.
8. Think of a time when developers did not empathise with you. In your experience, what made it difficult for them to empathise with you? Please share an example.
9. Think of a time when you did not empathise with developers. In your experience, what made it difficult for you to empathise with them? Please share an example.
10. Was there anything did to try and improve empathy? Why?
 - 10.1. Did you notice these empathy issues at the time?

Consequences of empathy and lack of empathy:

11. What did you experience when developers empathised with you?
 - 11.1. How did you feel?
 - 11.2. What happened as a result of their empathy?
 - 11.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?
 - 11.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
12. What did you experience when you empathised with developers?
 - 12.1. What happened as a result of your empathy?
 - 12.2. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?
 - 12.3. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
13. What did you experience when developers were not empathetic towards you? What was that like?
 - 13.1. How did you feel?
 - 13.2. What happened due to their lack of empathy?
 - 13.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
 - 13.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
14. What did you experience when you did not show empathy towards developers?
 - 14.1. What happened due to your lack of empathy?
 - 14.2. Have you had any negative experiences due to your lack of empathy?
 - 14.3. Have you had any positive experiences due to your lack of empathy?
15. What would you do to better empathise, or any strategies for mitigating the empathy barriers? What would work for you?
16. Is there anything else you would like to tell us?

B.3 Interview Guide of Software Developers - Round 2

In the second round, we prioritised questions on consequences early in the interviews to allocate more time to explore the consequences of empathy and lack of empathy.

1. Besides other developers, who are the stakeholders you are interacting with?
 - 1.1. Can you briefly explain what your interaction with them looks like?
 - 1.2. What is the mode of communication? How frequently do you meet?
2. What comes to your mind when you hear the word empathy? How do you describe empathy?
 - 2.1. What does empathy mean to you when interacting with these stakeholders?
3. When interacting with software developers, do you think these stakeholders need to practise empathy? Why?
4. Do you think empathy is relevant when considering your work and your interactions with these stakeholders? Why or why not? Please can you provide an example.
5. On a scale of 1 (useless) - 5 (useful), how would you rate empathy when interacting with stakeholders? Why?

Consequences of empathy and lack of empathy:

6. Think of a time when these stakeholders empathised with you. What did you experience when these stakeholders empathised with you? Please share an example.
 - 6.1. How did you feel?
 - 6.2. What happened as a result of their empathy?
 - 6.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?
 - 6.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
7. Think of a time when you empathised with these stakeholders. What did you experience when you empathised with these stakeholders? Please share an example.
 - 7.1. What happened as a result of your empathy?
 - 7.2. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?
 - 7.3. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
8. Think of a time when these stakeholders did not empathise with you. What did you experience when these stakeholders were not empathetic towards you? What was that like? Please share an example.
 - 8.1. How did you feel?
 - 8.2. What happened due to their lack of empathy?
 - 8.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
 - 8.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
9. Think of a time when you did not empathise with these stakeholders. What did you experience when you did not show empathy towards stakeholders? Please share an example.
 - 9.1. What happened due to your lack of empathy?
 - 9.2. Have you had any negative experiences due to your lack of empathy?
 - 9.3. Have you had any positive experiences due to your lack of empathy?

Causes of empathy and lack of empathy:

10. Referring back to the previous example you shared when stakeholders showed empathy towards you, in your experience, what made it easier for them to empathise with you?
11. Referring back to the previous example you shared when you showed empathy towards stakeholders, what made it easier for you to empathise with them?
12. Referring back to the previous example you shared when stakeholders did not show empathy towards you, in your experience, what made it difficult for them to empathise with you?
13. Referring back to the previous example you shared when you did not show empathy towards stakeholders, what made it difficult for you to empathise with them?

14. Was there anything did to try and improve empathy? Why?
 - 14.1. Did you notice these empathy issues at the time?
15. What would you do to better empathise, or any strategies for mitigating the empathy barriers? What would work for you?
16. Is there anything else you would like to tell us?

B.4 Interview Guide of Software Stakeholders - Round 2

In the second round, we prioritised questions on consequences early in the interviews to allocate more time to explore the consequences of empathy and lack of empathy.

1. Can you briefly explain what your interactions with developers look like?
 - 1.1. What is the mode of communication? How frequently do you meet?
2. What comes to your mind when you hear the word empathy? How do you describe empathy?
 - 2.1. What does empathy mean to you when interacting with developers?
3. When interacting with stakeholders, do you think software developers need to practise empathy? Why?
4. Do you think empathy is relevant when considering your work and your interactions with developers? Why or why not? Please can you provide an example.
5. On a scale of 1 (useless) - 5 (useful), how would you rate empathy when interacting with developers? Why?

Consequences of empathy and lack of empathy:

6. Think of a time when developers empathised with you. What did you experience when developers empathised with you? Please share an example.
 - 6.1. How did you feel?
 - 6.2. What happened as a result of their empathy?
 - 6.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?

- 6.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
7. Think of a time when you empathised with developers. What did you experience when you empathised with developers? Please share an example.
 - 7.1. What happened as a result of your empathy?
 - 7.2. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their empathy?
 - 7.3. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their empathy?
8. Think of a time when developers did not empathise with you. What did you experience when developers were not empathetic towards you? What was that like? Please share an example.
 - 8.1. How did you feel?
 - 8.2. What happened due to their lack of empathy?
 - 8.3. Have you had any negative experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
 - 8.4. Have you had any positive experiences as a result of their lack of empathy?
9. Think of a time when you did not empathise with developers. What did you experience when you did not show empathy towards developers? Please share an example.
 - 9.1. What happened due to your lack of empathy?
 - 9.2. Have you had any negative experiences due to your lack of empathy?
 - 9.3. Have you had any positive experiences due to your lack of empathy?

Causes of empathy and lack of empathy:

10. Referring back to the previous example you shared when developers empathised with you, in your experience, what made it easier for them to empathise with you?
11. Referring back to the previous example you shared when you empathised with developers, can you explain what made it easier for you to empathise with them?
12. Referring back to the previous example you shared when developers did not empathise with you, in your experience, what made it difficult for them to empathise with you?
13. Referring back to the previous example you shared when you did not empathise with developers, can you explain what made it difficult for you to empathise with them?
14. Was there anything did to try and improve empathy? Why?
 - 14.1. Did you notice these empathy issues at the time?
15. What would you do to better empathise, or any strategies for mitigating the empathy barriers? What would work for you?
16. Is there anything else you would like to tell us?